

Modern shops and modern shapes: registration versus regeneration

Introduction

Today, shopping has become a vital part of modern city-life, although it was not mentioned explicitly when CIAM analysed the Functional City. Fueled by the booming economy and globalization, the impact of retailing on urban development has increased. Shops and shopping centres reflect the fast change of fashions and of spending patterns, but they also change due to social and technical reasons. So, function, form and future do not always coincide, when the conservation of early post-war shopping centres is concerned. The question is if conservation of such dynamic concepts is desirable and to what extent. The Dutch Lijnbaan ensemble of shops and towerblocks, designed in the early 50's and regarded world-widely as an important model of urban renewal, offers us a good test case to confront two of DOCOMOMO's concerns: registration versus regeneration.

Postwar Prototype

The Lijnbaan ensemble is the remarkable result of public-private cooperation, economy and inventiveness and is an essential element of the urban and commercial reparation of Rotterdam's devastated city heart. After the bombardments of May 1940 only a few pre-war buildings had survived, mainly along the Coolsingel, which used to be one of the main cross-roads through the historic town centre. In the early '40s many remnants were cleared for an almost *tabula rasa* situation – then welcomed as a fortune of war by the modernist architects and town planners and enabled by a system of expropriation, compen-

sation and rebuilding obligation. In 1946 the ASRO (advisory bureau of Rotterdam's city plan, headed by Cees van Traa), presented its radical *Basisplan* for rebuilding the inner city with wider streets and a shift of functions. In conjunction with new west-bound traffic-routes (Maastunnel, Central railway station), a new shopping centre was conceived west of the Coolsingel, an area where such a commercial concentration had never been before.

According to this plan dozens of duped city-shopkeepers had to move from the old, small-scaled Hoogstraat to five new city courtyards. Because they had neither money nor materials to make a fresh start, they were not very keen to make extra investments for upper dwellings and offices over the shops. Moreover, they discovered the success of both the low-rise emergency shops (accommodated in aligned wooden barracks) and the large-scaled models of collective accommodation like the *Industrieflats* and the *Groothandelsgebouw* (at that time under construction). About 65 shopkeepers had allied forces to develop an affordable shopping centre and in consultation with the authorities, architects and finance companies, the idea originated to separate not only the shops from the dwellings, but also the pedestrian routes from the traffic roads. So, by irony of fate it was as a result of the shopkeepers' poor position that the revolutionary concept of a traffic-free shopping centre emerged, the first in Europe, which would become a prototype of prosperity.

Almost from the start the active, modernist architect Jo van den Broek had been involved in this project. He associated with Jaap Bakema in 1948 (as successors of Brinkman & Van der Vlugt's office) and was aided by Frans van Gool for the architectural details of the shopping centre after 1950, while Hugh Maaskant and others had the supervision of the U-shaped flat blocks at the west. They merged urban and architectural design in a unique, orthogonal ensemble with alternating low- and high-rised blocks which had to fit in a new city layout between some damaged *pièces de résistance* from the past, like the Atlanta hotel and the Coolsingel hospital. The L-shaped core of the Lijnbaan consisted of two intersecting pedestrian promenades, unusually broad (18 m) to allow sunshine.

The short wing broadened towards a higher square opposite the surviving Townhall along the Coolsingel, while the main wing was laid out parallel to this North-South boulevard. The shop rows were linked by free hanging awnings (giving shade and shelter) and surrounded by service roads at the rear. In order to organise the 'unity in variety' two basic shop types were available: the normal type with a basement and two equal levels or the split-leveltype with

entresol. Maximum flexibility was allowed by the use of concrete frames, partition walls of brick and facade elements of vibrated concrete, based on a module of 1,10 m. This scheme was subdivided in cornershops and terraced shops, which varied in depth according to their location along the short wing (15 m) or the main promenade (20 m); only Meddens' fashion house had a bigger size, as a cornerstone at the crossing with the Townhall square. Although each shop could express its individual identity, many shopkeepers liked the same type of details (in shopfronts, advertisements, interiors) and often contracted the same architects. Many efforts were made to define the shopping area as a whole, beginning with the placement of its name in neon-letters above the main entrances. Also the continuous horizontality of the flat roofs, wood-clad awnings and arcades as well as the coloured pavement (which repeated the 1,10 m module) supported an impression of uniformity and harmony. Even the telephone-boxes (Van der Vlugt's pre-war standardtype) and standardized lampposts stressed the over-all appearance of cohesion and modernity. The public space of the promenades was carefully furnished with flowerboxes, aviaries, kiosks, trees and benches to create a cozy atmosphere, while outer display cases, glazed shopfronts and well-tempered lighting were meant to invite the wandering public in to shop.

In 1953 the Lijnbaan shopping centre was opened officially by the Minister of Reconstruction and Housing. From the start it was a great success; the Lijnbaan promoted shopping as a leisure-time activity; people came in crowds, excited about the modern spaces of illusion, an open-air recall of the (bombed) nineteenth century arcade. Shortly following the opening attractions typical for city-life were added like pavement cafés, restaurants and cinemas. Far south, at the Binnenwegplein behind the hospital, the great stores of De Klerk and Ter Meulen, Wassen, van Vorst formed the first demonstrations of Van den Broek and Bakema's capability to invent new shopping types. To the southwest, the *Bijenkorf* department store was given a new location (designed by M. Breuer and A. Elzas, 1954-57, and causing the final demolition of Dudok's pre-war creation near the Leuvehaven); at the other side of the Coolsingel – just between the pre-war Stock Exchange and the ruined Laurens church – the *Galeries Modernes* and other new shop buildings took shape in a great variety of sizes and styles.

Surrounded by the commercial magnets and city facilities (and tower blocks with greens) and embellished by several bronze sculptures, the Lijnbaan prototype could not be followed in its full 'downtown' character. But the arrangement of terraced, similar shops linked with awnings and provided with

some public facilities and parking areas was copied frequently in new town town extensions. In fact, the Lijnbaan and these neighbourhood shopping centres could not function without each other. They were both part of a modernist vision of urban planning, in which the post-war concepts of 'urban core' and 'neighbourhood unit' were balanced in a functional hierarchy. Gradually, the idea to create a traffic-free shopping nucleus was transferred to already existing historic centres and adopted also in the central-east shopping area around the Hoogstraat during the late 60's.

Circulation and Transformation

In every respect – street profile, appearance, accessibility, combination of retail and amusement – the Lijnbaan meant an inversion of the situation in historic shopping areas. The predominant feature was the strict spatial organisation of the total shopping process, from logistics to display, like a commercial machine. The efficient routing and the consistent concept of dynamity were positively inspired by American experiences (Van der Broek had visited the States in 1948). But the separated circulation of people, goods and cars was rather a critical response to the growing annoyance caused by motorised traffic in inner cities. Although in the recovering Netherlands of the 50's the private use of automobiles was not as heavy as in the USA, it was banned from the shopping promenades; even bikers were not allowed to drive in the Lijnbaan. All was designed at a human scale and to foster the slow tempo of pedestrians being lured to consume, encouraged by glazed show-cases and shopfronts, often showcasing an open connection with the interiors. Inside the shops the tempting display and controlled circulation were continued in various ways, according to the ideas of the shopkeepers and their architects.

The freedom for individual detailing was as accepted within the general architectural framework as was the supposition that most shopfronts would change over time. Therefore, the architectural aesthetic was restrained and restricted to the thoughtful proportioning and subdivision of standardized elements. Overall, a certain quality and consistency was supposed for the kind of shops at the Lijnbaan.

More extensions were foreseen when the old Coolsingel hospital was scheduled to be removed, which was the case in 1963. Hence the Lijnbaan promenade could be extended southwards and a traverse built over the promenade – this was intended for the Rotterdam Art Foundation to bring art closer to the public. Underground new shopping spaces were created, accessible by a *tapis roulant*, but this was only in use for a few months. The traverse (1968) connected the great stores of Ter Meulen and De

Klerk, which were extended at the same time, also under the supervision of Van den Broek and Bakema, while a 100 year old plane-tree and the former hospital porch recalled the pre-war conditions at this spot (now named Lijnbaan square).

In the late 60's both the economy and leisure-time (free Saturday) had made so much progress that the naive scheme for car parking failed. The initial idea was that the cars of shopkeepers, residents and customers could take the same plots successively, for which 2180 plots with parking meters were reserved at the nearby Theatre square and the adjacent streets. But soon it became apparent that a substantial increase in spaces would be needed; this was to be realised by means of one underground and three multistoried parking garages (1968-72). Meanwhile, the general traffic circulation through and around the city increased, facilitated by new infrastructure and new high-rise office blocks affected the use and standing of the Lijnbaan ensemble as it had been during the first two decades, but this was nothing compared to more recent transformations.

Recent developments

However modern the Lijnbaan was in its urban and architectural concept, the traditional commercial concept of individual shopkeepers selling specialised goods became out-dated within twenty years. Only the great department stores at the southern ends foreshadowed the increasing scale and 'Retailing Revolution' which took place from the 70's onwards. Due to the growing competition with other shopping centres and attractions – often more easily accessible by car than the down-town Lijnbaan – as well as the incursion of international chain stores and the change of generations, many shops have changed their original character, not only in appearance (fronts, advertisements, interiors), but also in standing and ownership. Generally spoken, a decline of quality can be seen in the central pedestrian area, while the 'better' shops can be found along the traffic road of the outer west side, where also some new shopbuildings have been built at the former side-entrances to the towerblocks. Just a few 'originals' have resisted the assaults of flashy fashion and fast food shops and recent modernization: Meddens' fashion house, Koch's art shop and Heetman's jewellery. But they, too, had to take precautions against vandalism and crime. Roll-down shutters have reduced the fun of windowshopping after half past five. Neon lights in screaming colours and muzak create both visual and acoustic dissonance, not to speak of ugly stands, litter and the general degradation of the public space. In addition to the negative effects of recent social and economic development, new requirements and build-

ing regulations for safety, energy-saving, and accessibility have led to radical rebuilding of facades and interiors. Remarkably, the rear sides are essentially unchanged, except for the colour scheme.

However, two interventions of the late 90's have changed the Lijnbaan completely, apart from the conspicuous reshaping of the adjacent Theatre square (Adriaan Geuze). One is the total refurbishing of the public space, from pavement to canopy, from bench to telephone and flower boxes in new shapes, materials and colours. When it became apparent that a complete covering of the pedestrian area would be too expensive, the shopkeepers decided to contract the original architect's office (still under the name of Van den Broek and Bakema but run by a new generation) for another kind of facelift. Despite consultation with the municipal Commission on external appearance, this facelift resulted in the further disappearance of original architectural details, including the Lijnbaan neonlights above the main entrances. At the same time one could say that there is a continuity of architectural involvement, function and urban design.

The other transformation concerned the complicated insertion of a semi-underground shopping area to reconnect at last the eastern shopping area with the Lijnbaan, in combination with the subwaystation. The official name of this American-Dutch shopping street (The Jerde Partnership and Architectencie.) is 'Beurstraverse' (Stock Exchange arcade), but it attained instant popularity under the nickname 'Koopgoot' ('sale gully'), as a result of the coincident implementation of the liberal policy of the mid-90's to allow shopping partly on Sundays.

Despite this new commercial success, the loss of several typical shopbuildings by reputed architects from the early post-war years was severely felt, particularly by a small group of local art historians. This group instigated a campaign to conserve the 'heritage of the reconstruction' (1940-65), which soon also involved architects, politicians and conservation authorities. The Reconstruction Committee pleaded for a new approach to the conservation and recognition of the post-war heritage by exploring existing zoning regulations and a method of design oriented study, as well as initiating a systematic inventory of the remaining buildings within the rebuilt city heart. For instance, a multi-disciplinary team investigated by visual means the functional and architectural opportunities for the re-use Huf's shoe store, a small glass palace while respecting its transparency. In addition, an expert commission was appointed to evaluate the urban and architectural qualities of Rotterdam's inner city, which resulted in the advisory report *Het gebruik van de stad* (1997, The use of the city) and developed an analytical

vocabulary and 'policy toolkit' for recent heritage under the motto *Let Rotterdam be itself*. Without mentioning any particular case, all conclusions and recommendations concerning protective measures in combination with a powerful and creative vision on future developments are valid for the Lijnbaan ensemble, which is depicted many times in this report. Nevertheless, new initiatives in favour of very high towerblocks (over 180 m) to be built at the expense of two characteristic cinemas and the Jungerhans shop flanking the Lijnbaan, will test the strength of these recommendations and the present zoning rules in practice.

Dealing with dilemmas

The recent developments give reason to approach the Lijnbaan ensemble from a DOCOMOMO point of view. An analogy springs to mind with the conservation paradox of Zonnestraal's sanatorium, which was designed as a 'disposable building' but is designated as a protected monument because of its innovative concept, despite later alterations and its ruinous condition. In the *Advisory Report to ICOMOS (The Modern Movement and the World Heritage List, 1997, p. 10)* it is stated that "in spite of its intentional transitoriness, the architecture of the Modern Movement is now an essential part of our cultural heritage and therefore deserves conservation. This implies that some replacement of original materials and other alterations are acceptable, as long as the architect's concept (idea) in the present form, space and appearance of a building or site are still recognisable. However, materials, construction and details remain important for the 'test of authenticity', to support and to realise the abstract 'idea' of the Modern architect."

The original idea of the Lijnbaan ensemble – terraced shops around a pedestrian nucleus, towerblocks and public gardens – is still recognisable, though it has lost much of its former glory. Other testing criteria give more difficulties. How does one classify the three shops which now deviate from the new re-styling by keeping the original architectural detailing – as obsolete anomalies or as treasures of material authenticity? At least these buildings deserve careful documentation, which can be useful as a starting point for future plans of maintenance and/or alteration, not only for these particular shops but also for the others. Additional documentation could also come from archival research, particularly at the Netherlands Architectural Institute where the original drawings are held. But what becomes of the knowledge that the original colour scheme has been changed almost everywhere? Keep it in memory; as reconstruction would be too radical a solution.

Apart from the 'material' changes of most shops and the public space, 'immaterial' change can be noticed now in the public perception and use of the shopping centre. A thorough exercise in 'commercial archaeology' would be necessary to find out who occupied the Lijnbaan in its very beginning. If possible, a new commercial upgrading to the original standards would be desirable, but that is most difficult to establish in the current, liberal economy with world-wide private ownership. The question of how to handle the popular, but ugly fastfood stands and temporary signs now blocking the original vistas will only be resolved through an open, voluntary dialogue between authorities, owners and local inhabitants about improving this situation. Therefore, more general measures of prevention and surveillance are needed which have nothing to do with any form of conservation. It is already a great step that some voluntary agreements have been made about the permanent shop advertisements, which is not easy with 83 different shopkeepers.

Following the pleas for protective measures, the municipality of Rotterdam has listed recently about 30 post-war buildings to be protected, including the *Groothandelsgebouw*, *Bijenkorf*, *Huf* and some other notable shop buildings but not the Lijnbaan ensemble, because of too many complications. However, in the – updated – International Selection of the Dutch DOCOMOMO working party both the Lijnbaan and the *Groothandelsgebouw* are included, thus beginning the serious evaluation of Modern architecture after 1940. The Netherlands Department for Conservation, having just started a plan of action on post-war heritage, has also recognized these buildings as national highlights which need special attention or even protection as soon as the 50 year rule applies.

It is here that an eventual conflict of interests between registration and regeneration could arise. To commercial proprietors any limitation in the use of their properties is unwelcome: they like to adapt their shops to new trends. Rightly they could refer to the original concept (were they to know it) which was meant for change and individual expression. The problem is that we, as experts, do not like the results of bad taste or the ignorance of the original features.

Because shopping is a basic function of modern city life, even an essential part of economic developments, a careful approach is needed to keep the ageing shopping centres alive, firstly in function but also in form. Since Rotterdam is not the only modern city facing this problem, an international exchange of knowledge has been started (thanks to DOCOMOMO contacts) with another harbour city with a modernist city heart: Le Havre (France). Here the national rule of urban conservation (ZZPAUP,

Zone de Protection du Patrimoine Architectural, Urbaine et Paysager) has been brought into operation, together with an educational and contact program for the shopkeepers, who are mostly the same kind of retailers as in the 50's. Just as the rigid reconstruction plan itself, under the supervision of old Auguste Perret, the French method is full of detailed guidance and centralistic tendencies, which cannot be translated completely in the same way in free Rotterdam, proud of its dynamity. Perhaps a mixture can be distilled with the policy model on the Miesian shopping centre in the English new town Milton Keynes of the 70's, where the involved owners have undersigned voluntary an agreement with the local authorities on a common architectural treatment. More examples can be added to demonstrate that

DOCOMOMO's register work and professional network can act as an important tool to develop new strategies and extend the knowledge how to deal with the dilemma's of Modern shops.

In conclusion, the idea of 'integrated conservation' by using the available planning instruments and a weighty section on the cultural-historical values in every development plan as well as a voluntary commitment of the private owners seems to be a good option to solve the tensions between documentation, conservation and transformation in order to keep the 'commercial' legacy of the Modern Movement as a *living heritage*. The Modern shopping centres of the 50's deserve a second chance and a detailed documentation as a source of inspiration for future developments.

Fig. 1 – Lijnbaan shopping promenade in the fifties, with original awnings, pavement, telephone box and aviary, designed by J.H. van den Broek, J.B. Bakema, F.J. van Gool, H.A. Maaskant, A. Krijgsman and H.D. Bakker in 1949-1954 for the reconstruction of Rotterdam's devastated city heart.

Fig. 2 – Schematic variants for the shops along the Lijnbaan.

Fig. 3 – View of the restyled Lijnbaan, with shops, high-rised flat blocks, signs and new additions. Photo: RDMZ, Zeist, 1999.

Fig. 4 – View of the restyled shopping promenade with new awnings, neons, benches and pavement. Photo: RDMZ, Zeist, 1999.

Fig. 5 – View of the short wing of the Lijnbaan in the direction of the surviving Townhall from 1911-19 with new elements (and litter). Photo: RDMZ, Zeist, 1999.

Fig. 6 – Front of Koch's art shop, the only remaining authentic element of the original layout of the Lijnbaan. Photo: RDMZ, Zeist, 1999.

Fig. 7 – Rear of Koch's art shop and adjacent shops along the expedition street. Photo: RDMZ, Zeist, 1999.

Fig. – 8 Interior of Koch's art shop with staircase. Photo: RDMZ, Zeist, 1999.

Fig. 9 – View of the Schouwburgplein (Theatre square), restyled by Adriaan Geuze, with the Lijnbaan flatblocks. Photo by Marieke Kuipers, 2000.

Fig. 10 – View of the Beustraverse, nicknamed Koopgoot ('sale gully'), with M. Breuer's Bijenkorf and the extended Stock Exchange at the left. Photo by Marieke Kuipers, 2000.

Fig. 11 – Le Havre, recommended extension variants for the flat and shop blocks.

Fig. 12 – Rotterdam, Lijnbaan flatblocks with green square still functioning according to the original intentions. Photo: RDMZ, Zeist, 1999.

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documenting and developing early shopping centres (Lijnbaan, Rotterdam).

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